

Quantum Spatial Density as an Independent Probability in Shannon's Entropy?

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Sept. 8, 2020

In the literature, one often finds a quantum expression for Shannon's entropy of the form: $-\langle W^*W \rangle \ln(W^*W)$ ((1)) where W^*W is spatial density i.e. $W(x)$ = the wavefunction. This implies $W^*(x)W(x)$ is an independent probability. Given that $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$, and $W^*W = \sum_{p_1, p_2} a(p_1)a(p_2) \exp(ip_1 x) \exp(ip_2 x)$, one may see that for $p_1 = -p_2$ in the latter with $a(p) = a(-p)$ leads to $\cos(p_1 x)$ terms. These are positive and negative in different x regions. In fact, in many cases, the overall spatial density exhibits peaks and valleys suggesting that $W^*(x)W(x)$ is correlated, i.e. not independent we argue. Furthermore, the form ((1)) uses only position when there is an expectation value for $\langle p^*p \rangle$ and $\langle p \rangle$, both functions of x , where p is momentum. Thus, the variance of p -ensemble average may change with x , yet position only is used in the computation of Shannon's entropy, which we argue seems unusual. In a previous note (1), we suggest using $a(p_1)\exp(ip_1 x) a(p_2)\exp(ip_2 x)$ as the probability for Shannon's entropy. This leads to a spatial form $2W \times dW/dx$ which matches ((1)) for the ground state of the quantum oscillator case. For the ground state oscillator, $W^*W = C \exp(-ax^2)$ i.e. a Gaussian. This suggests that for this case only, $W^*(x)W(x)$ represents an independent probability which may be used in Shannon's entropy, we argue. We attempt to consider these issues in this note.

Spatial Density versus $a(p_1)\exp(ip_1 x) a(p_2) \exp(ip_2 x)$ In Shannon's Entropy

One frequently sees $-\langle W^*W \rangle \ln[W^*W]$ as Shannon's quantum spatial entropy. This seems to imply that $W^*(x)W(x)$, the spatial density (a physical observable), behaves as an independent probability. In other words, at time t_1 a particle has a probability $P(x_1)$ to be at x_1 , at t_2 $P(x_2)$ to be at x_2 . Thus, one may form arrangements with different x values. At one instant, the particle may be at $x=0$ and the next at $x = a$ a very large number. This spatial density also completely ignores microscopic momentum and ensemble average momentum considerations.

In (1), we considered Shannon's entropy using $a(p_1)\exp(ip_1 x) a(p_2)\exp(ip_2 x)$ which yields a spatial term of $2W \times dW/dx$ ((2)) which takes into consideration both spatial and average velocity ($d \ln(W)/dx$) considerations.

Interestingly, the two spatial terms, ((1)) and ((2)), are identical for the ground state of the harmonic oscillator $W(x) = C \exp(-ax^2)$. Otherwise, they seem to be different. Thus, if one is to use ((2)), there must be a reason for not using ((1)). We try to argue that for the oscillator ground state, one has a Gaussian which suggests independent random positions according to the Central Limit Theorem. Thus in such a case, using $W^*(x)W(x)$ as an independent probability seems to be fine. For higher oscillator states, however, entropies ((1)) and ((2)) seem to differ. We try to argue that $W^*(x)W(x)$ is not an independent probability in other cases.

Consider: $W^*(x)W(x) = \sum_{p_1, p_2} a(p_1)\exp(ip_1 x) a(p_2) \exp(ip_2 x)$

If $a(p)=a(-p)$ (for example) and one considers p_1+p_2 and $-p_1-p_2$, one obtains $\cos((p_1+p_2)x)$ which is an oscillating function. Thus, there seems to be a correlation between different x points. At some x , p_1+p_2 gives a positive value (i.e. adds to spatial density) and at others, it subtracts, even though there is the same probability to have p_1 and p_2 . Thus, if this feature follows for all p_1+p_2 terms i.e. the spatial density has humps and valleys (which it often does-for example excited oscillator states), then these seem to be correlated and not independent. In some places, the $\cos((p_1+p_2)x)$ terms cancel with others to yield a very low spatial density. We have argued in previous notes that this represents reverse motion due to a stochastic potential which only equals $V(x)$ on average, but takes the form $\sum_k V(k) \exp(ikx)$. In other cases, the terms combine to give a peak spatial density value. Thus, there is an underlying almost collective motion (back and forth) behind the peak and valley spatial density probabilities. It thus seems difficult to argue for independence of probability $=W^*(x)W(x)$. If a particle is in a momentum state p_1 at x and receives a hit moving at x moving it to p_2 , then the product of relative probabilities is $a(p_1)\exp(ip_1x)a(p_2)\exp(ip_2x)$. This seems to govern where the particle will go.

A second argument we wish to consider is that of variance of average velocity.

Variance of Average Velocity

In classical statistical mechanics, the probability for a system with a potential $V(x)$ is: $C \exp(-1/T(.5mv^2 + V(x)))$. Thus a spatial density exists, but the statistical feature is that at any point x : $f(e_1)f(e_2)=f(e_3)f(e_4)$ where $e_i=pi^2/2m$ and $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$. Thus, the statistical distribution of the velocities is the same at any x point and the variance is a constant related to temperature. If one moves from one point to another, the overall spatial density changes, but the velocity distribution and variance is unchanged.

In quantum mechanics, the picture seems to differ. At time t_1 , a particle may have momentum p_1 at x with a probability $a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$. At a later time, it may have a different momentum at x . Thus, there is an average momentum at x and an average kinetic energy (which equals the classical result).

$$\langle p \rangle = [\sum_p p a(p) \exp(ipx)]/W(x) \text{ and } \langle p^2 \rangle = [\sum_p p^2 a(p) \exp(ipx)]/W(x) \quad ((3))$$

In general $\langle p \rangle \langle p \rangle$ does not equal $\langle p^2 \rangle$ and both are functions of x . One may calculate an x dependent variance for $\langle p \rangle$. Thus, the distribution of velocities or momenta changes at different x points and the variance may change too. If a particle is at x_1 at time t_1 with a probability $W^*(x)W(x)$, there is a particular ensemble average momentum variance. At another x point where spatial probability is $W^*(x)W(x)$ the ensemble average momentum variance has another value. It seems one does not simply move from one x point to another independently (we argue), ignoring considerations of ensemble average momentum.

For the ground state oscillator, one may note that momentum variance is constant for all x . Thus, using ensemble averages, even though average p changes with x , its variance does not. In such a case, one may perhaps ignore velocity considerations and consider $W^*(x)W(x)$ as describing the probability to be used for Shannon's entropy.

Oscillator ground state $W(x)=C \exp(-ax^2)$

$$\langle p \rangle = \int p W^*(x)W(x) dx = \int p (-i\hbar \frac{d}{dx} W) W dx = -i\hbar \int p \frac{d}{dx} (W^2) dx = -i\hbar \frac{1}{2} \frac{d}{dx} \int W^2 dx = 0$$

$$\langle p^2 \rangle = \int p^2 W^*(x)W(x) dx = \int p^2 (-i\hbar \frac{d}{dx} W) W dx = \hbar^2 \int p \frac{d}{dx} (pW) dx = \hbar^2 \int p dp = 2m[E - \frac{1}{2}kx^2]$$

$$\text{Variance squared} = \langle p^2 \rangle - \langle p \rangle^2 = 2mE \quad \text{independent of } x$$

For excited states of the oscillator, this does not hold, so statistical behaviour of an ensemble average $\langle p \rangle$ usually changes with position.

For the ground state oscillator, there is forward and backward microscopic motion, but if one considers the ensemble average $\langle p \rangle$, its variance is constant with x . If one uses the variance as a measure of uncertainty spread of this ensemble average, then that is constant in x . It seems that the variance is used in Heisenberg's uncertainty principle, although this is not the variance calculated at each point x . Nevertheless, it seems that a varying $\langle p \rangle$ variance with x may indicate issues with using $W^*(x)W(x)$ as an independent probability which allows one to be at one precise x at one time and another at a different time.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we question whether $W^*(x)W(x)$ is an independent probability which may be used in Shannon's spatial entropy. We argue it may only be used in the case of the ground state of the quantum oscillator. In that situation, the variance of the ensemble average momentum is constant in x and one has a Gaussian wavefunction, usually associated with random motion. For other cases, we use $a(p_1)\exp(i p_1 x)a(p_2)\exp(i p_2 x)$ as the probability to use in Shannon's entropy which yields a spatial entropy of $2W \int x dW/dx$. For the oscillator ground state, this matches $W^*W \ln(W^*W)$, but not for other cases it seems..

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Relationship Between Entropy and Energy Densities in Quantum Mechanics (preprint, zenodo, 2020)